

IMPLEMENTATION OF A SCALE FOR ASSESSING MAXILLOFACIAL FRACTURES AND ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS

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Abstract. Quality of life assessment is increasingly being used in clinical medicine because it allows us to study the impact of disease on various components of a patient's health and identify additional benefits or drawbacks of treatment. The introduction of advanced quality of life assessment methods into clinical practice has provided access to important information about aspects of patient functioning. These data can be used to develop treatment and rehabilitation programs and monitor the patient's condition during treatment.

Keywords: Maxillofacial Fracture Scale and quality of life assessment in patients with concomitant maxillofacial trauma.

Relevance. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 1 million people die each year as a result of road traffic accidents (RTA), and 15-20 million suffer injuries of varying severity. In developing countries, RTAs are the leading cause of maxillofacial trauma. Meanwhile, in high-income countries, the most common causes of both TBI and maxillofacial injuries are domestic injuries, violence, falls from standing height, and catastrophes.

Due to its high prevalence, traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a widespread and significant public health and social issue, with high mortality and disability rates (global averages are 2-4 per 1,000 population per year), severe complications, and consequences, including permanent or temporary disability, imposing financial costs on families, society, and the state. The diagnosis of maxillofacial trauma is clinical and is established based on the patient's medical history, physical examination, and the results of instrumental examinations.

According to the literature, CT allows for the visualization of bones and soft tissues in any plane without summation. Multiplanar analysis of isotropic images obtained using MSCT allows for the diagnosis of both displaced and non-displaced fractures. MSCT is more sensitive than orthopantomography in diagnosing fractures of the angle, rami, and condyle of the mandible.

In the treatment of patients with moderate to severe brain contusions, their continuous hospitalization with dynamic monitoring using MSCT or MRI is essential to monitor the condition of the brain. A maxillofacial surgeon, in

accordance with the recommendations of the Association of Maxillofacial and Oral Surgeons, conducts a primary comprehensive examination of such a patient, determining damage to all anatomical structures of the maxillofacial region and indications for involving related specialists (otolaryngologist, neurologist, neurosurgeon, ophthalmologist, and resuscitation specialist) in the diagnostic process. These nosological manifestations are most frequently encountered in the clinical practice of dentists and neurologists. The presented results significantly expand our understanding of the pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, and new approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of these injuries.

When developing objective methods for assessing the severity of injuries, one of three approaches is used: 1. Anatomical - the severity criterion is the degree of anatomical destruction of tissues and organs. 2. Physiological - the severity criterion is physiological indicators, such as blood pressure and heart rate. 3. A combined approach uses both anatomical and physiological criteria.

Classification of Brain Contusions. According to the accepted Russian classification of trauma, mild, moderate, and severe brain contusions are classified based on the clinical course and severity of brain tissue damage. These contusions are also classified into three types: traumatic subarachnoid hemorrhage (TSH) and traumatic subarachnoid hemorrhage (TSH).

Moderate brain contusions occur in 49% of cases, mild in 33%, and severe in 18%. The severity of a brain contusion is determined by the degree of disturbance of consciousness, the severity of the patient's condition, the severity of neurological symptoms, and the results of instrumental (computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging of the brain) and laboratory tests.

Mild brain contusions are characterized by rapid recovery of consciousness after the initial loss of consciousness, which lasts for several minutes. The clinical picture is dominated by headache, nausea, vomiting, dizziness, and impaired attention and memory. Nystagmus (usually horizontal), asymmetry of reflexes, and sometimes mild hemiparesis may be detected.

Social and economic benefits. Cost-effectiveness: Using the maxillofacial fracture scale in the treatment of patients with combined maxillofacial and traumatic brain injuries reduces the costs of hospitalization, repeat surgeries, and additional laboratory tests. With the proposed maxillofacial fracture scale, hospitalization is reduced by 2-3 days. Among the 80 patients treated using the new method, complications were avoided. Savings: $200,000 \text{ soums} \times 2.5 \text{ days} \times 80 \text{ patients} = 40,000,000 \text{ soums}$. The average cost of one repeat surgery is 1,000,000 soums. Repeat interventions were avoided in 15 patients. Savings: 1,000,000

soums \times 15 patients = 15,000,000 soums. The cost of one analysis is 125,000 soums. The average number of studies per patient is 2. Savings: $125,000 \text{ soums} \times 2 \times 80 \text{ patients} = 20,000,000 \text{ soums}$. Total savings: $40,000,000 \text{ soums} + 15,000,000 \text{ soums} + 20,000,000 \text{ soums} = 75,000,000 \text{ soums}$. Annual savings: with an average annual number of patients of 150 people $75,000,000 \text{ soums} \times (150 / 80) = 140,625,000 \text{ soums}$. Conclusion: The use of the maxillofacial fracture scale in the treatment of patients with combined maxillofacial injuries resulted in savings of 75,000,000 sum (80 patients) per year, and 140,625,000 sum over the course of an annual practice, of which 112,500,000 sum are budgetary funds and 28,125,000 sum are extra-budgetary funds.

Thus, the use of the maxillofacial fracture scale in the treatment of patients with combined maxillofacial injuries reduces hospitalization and treatment costs, as the patient is referred to a professional specialist where they will receive medical care, which is a very important point.

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